

COMPARISON OF LIPID PROFILE IN TYPE 2 DIABETIC PATIENTS ON INSULIN VERSUS ORAL HYPOGLYCAEMIC AGENTS IN THE TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17906763>

Keywords

Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2;
Dyslipidemias; Insulin, Regular;
Hypoglycemic Agents; Cholesterol

Article History

Received: 25 May 2025

Accepted: 25 June 2025

Published: 30 June 2025

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Abstract

Background:

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a major global health concern, with cardiovascular complications largely driven by dyslipidemia. Oral hypoglycemic agents and insulin are central to glycemic management, yet their effects on lipid metabolism may differ. This study compares lipid profiles in T2DM patients receiving insulin versus those on oral hypoglycemic agents, with implications for cardiovascular risk reduction.

Materials and Methods:

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad, from November 2024 to April 2025, enrolling 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus equally divided into insulin and oral hypoglycemic agent groups. Participants had at least one year's disease duration, were on monotherapy for six months, and had a recent lipid profile. Demographic, clinical, and laboratory data were collected, and statistical analysis was performed in SPSS v23.0 with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

A total of 120 patients with T2DM were enrolled, equally divided between insulin and OHA groups. Both groups had comparable glycemic control (HbA1c: 7.82% vs. 8.05%, $p = 0.140$), but lipid parameters differed significantly. OHA users had higher total cholesterol, non-HDL cholesterol, and triglycerides, along with lower HDL-C compared to insulin users (all $p < 0.05$). The prevalence of low HDL-C and hypertriglyceridemia was also markedly greater in the OHA group.

Conclusion:

In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, oral hypoglycemic agent therapy was associated with higher triglycerides, lower HDL-C, and a greater burden of dyslipidemia compared to insulin, despite similar glycemic control. These findings highlight the importance of considering lipid effects when tailoring antidiabetic therapy. Larger prospective studies are needed to validate these results and elucidate underlying mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) accounting for the majority of cases.¹ Current estimates suggest that approximately 6.28% of the global population is affected by T2DM.² Management of this chronic condition primarily relies on pharmacological interventions aimed at maintaining glycemic control and preventing long-term complications.³ Oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs) are often effective in the early stages; however, due to the progressive decline in β -cell function, most patients eventually require insulin therapy.⁴ Available antidiabetic agents include sulfonylureas, biguanides, meglitinides, thiazolidinediones, alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, and insulin. Among these, metformin (a biguanide) remains the most widely prescribed first-line therapy, often in combination with sulfonylureas, whereas insulin and its analogs continue to play a central role in advanced disease.^{5,6}

Despite adequate glycemic management, cardiovascular complications remain the major cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with T2DM.⁷ Atherosclerosis, accelerated by atherogenic dyslipidemia, is particularly prevalent in this population.⁸ Dyslipidemia in T2DM is characterized by elevated triglycerides, increased levels of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C), and reduced levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C).⁹ These lipid abnormalities, together with increased oxidative stress and impaired vascular function, contribute significantly to the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis in diabetic patients.¹⁰ The Residual Risk Reduction Initiative has highlighted atherogenic dyslipidemia as a major determinant of cardiovascular risk in individuals with insulin resistance.¹¹

Several studies have demonstrated that aggressive lipid-lowering therapy, particularly targeting LDL-C, reduces the incidence of cardiovascular events in diabetic patients.¹² Furthermore, the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) provided compelling evidence that improved

glycemic control reduces microvascular complications, although its effect on macrovascular disease is less definitive.¹³ Despite these advances, the precise mechanisms underlying accelerated atherogenesis in diabetes remain incompletely understood.¹⁴

Given the central role of dyslipidemia in cardiovascular risk among diabetic patients, understanding the impact of different therapeutic strategies on lipid metabolism is of clinical importance. Insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents may influence lipid profiles differently, potentially affecting long-term cardiovascular outcomes. The present study aims to compare lipid profiles in patients with T2DM receiving insulin therapy versus those managed with oral hypoglycemic agents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital (FGPC), Islamabad, after approval by the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was carried out over six months, from November 2024 to April 2025, and all data were anonymized to maintain patient confidentiality.

The study population comprised adults aged 30–70 years with a confirmed diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) of at least one year's duration. Patients were eligible if they had been receiving either insulin therapy alone or oral hypoglycemic agents (metformin and/or sulfonylureas) alone for at least six months before enrollment, with a recent fasting lipid profile available within the preceding three months. Patients on combined insulin and OHA therapy, those using lipid-modifying agents other than statins, or with secondary causes of dyslipidemia such as hypothyroidism, nephrotic syndrome, or chronic liver disease were excluded. Individuals with recent acute illness or hospitalization within the past three months were also not included.

Sample size estimation using the WHO calculator indicated a minimum of 55 participants per group; however, to account for potential missing data, 60 patients were recruited into each group, giving a

total of 120 participants. Consecutive eligible patients who provided written informed consent were enrolled. Data collection was performed using a structured proforma, documenting demographic characteristics (age, sex, body mass index, smoking history, and duration of diabetes), clinical details (blood pressure, treatment type and duration, statin use), and laboratory results [HbA1c, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), triglycerides, and non-HDL cholesterol]. All biochemical tests were conducted in the institutional laboratory using standardized enzymatic methods.

The primary exposure variable was treatment modality (insulin versus oral hypoglycemic agents), while outcome variables included fasting lipid profile parameters. Potential confounders considered were age, sex, body mass index, duration of diabetes, HbA1c, and statin use. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation for normally distributed data or median with interquartile range for skewed data, while categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages. Between-group comparisons were made using the independent-samples t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and the chi-square or Fisher's

exact test for categorical variables. A two-tailed p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were included, with 60 participants in each treatment group. The mean age of the insulin group was significantly lower compared to the OHA group (52.8 ± 7.3 vs. 58.0 ± 8.5 years, $p < 0.001$). The proportion of male patients did not differ significantly between the two groups (51.7% vs. 65.0%, $p = 0.195$). Glycemic control, as measured by HbA1c, was comparable between the insulin and OHA groups ($7.82 \pm 1.05\%$ vs. $8.05 \pm 1.01\%$, $p = 0.140$).

In terms of lipid parameters, patients on OHA therapy had significantly higher mean total cholesterol (205.3 ± 41.4 vs. 190.7 ± 29.6 mg/dL, $p = 0.028$) and non-HDL cholesterol (166.3 ± 43.7 vs. 142.9 ± 31.7 mg/dL, $p = 0.001$) compared to those on insulin. LDL-C was higher in the OHA group but did not reach statistical significance (116.0 ± 30.3 vs. 107.6 ± 29.2 mg/dL, $p = 0.125$). HDL-C was significantly lower among OHA users (38.9 ± 9.6 vs. 47.8 ± 10.1 mg/dL, $p < 0.001$). Median triglyceride levels were also markedly elevated in the OHA group compared to the insulin group (211.2 [156.7-276.1] vs. 137.4 [101.1-165.9] mg/dL, $p < 0.001$) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline demographics and fasting lipid profile (n = 120)

MEASURE	INSULIN (N = 60)	OHA (N = 60)	p-VALUE*
Age, years (mean \pm SD)	52.8 ± 7.3	58.0 ± 8.5	0.000
Male – n (%)	31 (51.7%)	39 (65.0%)	0.195
HbA1c, % (mean \pm SD)	7.82 ± 1.05	8.05 ± 1.01	0.140
Total cholesterol, mg/dL (mean \pm SD)	190.7 ± 29.6	205.3 ± 41.4	0.028
LDL-C, mg/dL (mean \pm SD)	107.6 ± 29.2	116.0 ± 30.3	0.125
HDL-C, mg/dL (mean \pm SD)	47.8 ± 10.1	38.9 ± 9.6	<0.001

Triglycerides, mg/dL median (IQR)	137.4 (101.1-165.9)	211.2 (156.7-276.1)	<0.001
Non-HDL, mg/dL (mean ± SD)	142.9 ± 31.7	166.3 ± 43.7	0.001

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Analysis of abnormal lipid categories revealed a trend toward more frequent elevated LDL-C in the OHA group compared with the insulin group (73.3% vs. 55.0%, p = 0.057). Low HDL-C was significantly more prevalent among OHA users (70.0% vs. 38.3%, p = 0.001), as were

hypertriglyceridemia (78.3% vs. 40.0%, p < 0.001). Elevated non-HDL cholesterol was also more common in the OHA group, although this difference did not reach statistical significance (76.7% vs. 63.3%, p = 0.163) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Abnormal lipid categories by treatment group (n = 120)

LIPID ABNORMALITY (CUTOFF)	INSULIN N (%) (N=60)	OHA N (%) (N=60)	p-VALUE*
LDL > 100 mg/dL	33 (55.0%)	44 (73.3%)	0.057
Low HDL (male <40, female <50)	23 (38.3%)	42 (70.0%)	0.001
Triglycerides >150 mg/dL	24 (40.0%)	47 (78.3%)	<0.001
Non-HDL >130 mg/dL	38 (63.3%)	46 (76.7%)	0.163

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Comparison of abnormal lipid categories between patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)

receiving insulin versus oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of abnormal lipid categories between patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) receiving insulin versus oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs).

DISCUSSION:

The management of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) typically begins with oral hypoglycemic agents, which act through distinct mechanisms to address underlying metabolic defects. As the disease progresses and β -cell function declines, many patients ultimately require insulin therapy to achieve adequate glycemic control.⁴ Insulin not only lowers plasma glucose by suppressing hepatic glucose output and enhancing peripheral uptake but also improves several associated metabolic disturbances.⁶ The overarching therapeutic objective in T2DM remains the optimization of glycemic control alongside regulation of blood pressure and lipid levels, thereby reducing the risk and severity of long-term vascular complications. In this comparative cross-sectional study of 120 patients with type 2 diabetes, we observed that, despite comparable glycemic control (HbA1c), patients treated with OHAs had a more atherogenic lipid profile: higher total cholesterol and non-HDL cholesterol, markedly higher triglycerides, and lower HDL-C, while LDL-C differences were not statistically significant. These findings are biologically plausible and broadly consistent with prior literature.

In our adjusted dataset HbA1c was similar between groups, removing a major and common confounder in lipid comparisons. Published studies repeatedly show a positive correlation between poor glycemic control and adverse lipid parameters (higher triglycerides and total cholesterol, lower HDL), so balancing HbA1c strengthens the inference that observed lipid differences are less likely to be entirely explained by hyperglycemia alone. Multiple observational reports and cross-sectional analyses corroborate the relationship between HbA1c and dyslipidemia.^{15,16}

The higher mean total cholesterol in the OHA group (205.3 vs 190.7 mg/dL, $p=0.028$) is consistent with studies showing regimen-specific effects on cholesterol. Metformin frequently produces modest reductions in total cholesterol compared with comparator regimens in meta-analyses, whereas some older oral regimens (particularly combinations including sulfonylureas) show less favorable effects. Thus, a

mixed OHA group (metformin \pm sulfonylurea) may present with higher TC relative to insulin-treated patients, especially if statin use differs between groups. Systematic reviews and randomized trials have documented modest TC reduction with metformin.¹⁷

LDL-C did not differ significantly between groups in our sample (116.0 vs 107.6 mg/dL, $p=0.125$). This aligns with heterogeneous findings in the literature: some studies report small LDL reductions with metformin or after initiating lipid-lowering therapy, while others show minimal or no change attributable solely to antidiabetic regimen. Given that LDL is strongly influenced by statin therapy and other lipid-lowering interventions (which we must report and adjust for in the manuscript), an absence of a statistically significant crude difference is not unexpected.^{18,19}

The OHA group had significantly lower HDL-C (38.9 vs 47.8 mg/dL, $p<0.001$). Several mechanisms may explain higher HDL in insulin-treated patients: insulin improves peripheral lipid handling, suppresses lipolysis and free fatty acid flux to the liver, and can favorably modify HDL particle composition and size after initiation. Clinical reports of insulin initiation show increases in HDL and changes toward larger, less atherogenic HDL particles in some cohorts. Conversely, sulfonylurea therapy has been associated in meta-analyses with reductions in HDL. Thus, the observed HDL difference is concordant with mechanistic expectations and prior empirical work.^{20,21}

The most pronounced difference in our dataset was triglycerides (median 211.2 vs 137.4 mg/dL, $p<0.001$). The literature supports that insulin therapy (or the metabolic state achieved with optimized insulin) can reduce fasting triglycerides by suppressing adipose lipolysis and hepatic VLDL overproduction, whereas inadequate glycemic control and certain OHAs (notably sulfonylureas in some studies) are associated with higher TG. Meta-analyses and comparative studies report that basal/physiologic insulin regimens effectively lower serum TG, a finding that dovetails with our data.²²

Non-HDL-C was significantly higher in the OHA group (166.3 vs 142.9 mg/dL, $p=0.001$). Non-

HDL-C captures all atherogenic apolipoprotein B-containing particles (LDL, VLDL, IDL), and in diabetic populations it often outperforms LDL-C as a predictor of cardiovascular risk. Our finding of higher non-HDL-C in the OHA cohort therefore translates into a potentially greater atherogenic burden, consistent with the interpretation that the OHA group carries a less favorable lipid phenotype. Prior cohort studies and guideline discussions support the clinical importance of non-HDL-C, particularly in T2DM.²³

The categorical analysis mirrors continuous data: significantly more patients on OHAs had low HDL and hypertriglyceridemia, whereas the proportion with LDL >100 mg/dL and non-HDL >130 mg/dL showed non-significant trends toward being higher in the OHA group. The elevated prevalence of the “atherogenic dyslipidemia” triad (high TG, low HDL, small dense LDL phenotype) among OHA patients is of clinical concern because this pattern is strongly linked to coronary risk in insulin-resistant states. Evidence implicating small dense LDL and the TG/HDL ratio as markers of residual risk in diabetes reinforces the clinical relevance of these categorical differences.²⁴

The limitation of this study includes the cross-sectional design which precludes causal inference: although the lipid pattern we observed is compatible with a protective effect of insulin or an adverse profile associated with certain OHAs, reverse causation and residual confounding remain possible.

CONCLUSION:

Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus receiving oral hypoglycemic agents demonstrated significantly higher triglyceride levels, lower HDL-C concentrations, and a greater prevalence of dyslipidemia compared to those managed with insulin therapy, despite comparable glycemic control. Given the well-established role of atherogenic dyslipidemia in cardiovascular risk, clinicians should consider the impact of antidiabetic therapy on lipid regulation when individualizing treatment strategies. Further longitudinal studies with larger cohorts are

warranted to confirm these associations and to clarify the underlying mechanisms.

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